

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

Ionic conductivity of $\text{Li}_2\text{O}-\text{P}_2\text{O}_5$ glasses from thermodynamic modeling of their chemical structureAlberto López-Grande¹ | Rajesh Dagupati² ¹Instituto de Cerámica y Vidrio (CSIC), Madrid, Spain²FunGlass, Alexander Dubček University, Trenčín, Slovakia³Departamento de Matemática Aplicada a la Ingeniería Industrial, E.T.S. Ingenieros Industriales, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, Madrid, Spain**Correspondence**

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Abstract

Modeling the transport properties of glasses, and ionic conductivity in particular, has been a recurrent issue motivated for their high interest in the rapid developing field of energy conversion and storage devices for a wide range of applications such as in lithium rechargeable batteries. Despite the absolute conductivity of phosphate-based glasses is not among the highest, their ease of preparation and ability to host transition metals and secondary anions has contributed to foster their research from which good examples are the LiPON electrolytes or the LATP-based glass ceramics. In this work, the structure and ionic conductivity of lithium phosphate glasses with nominal composition $x \text{Li}_2\text{O} \cdot (1-x) \text{P}_2\text{O}_5$, and x between 46 and 58 mol%, have been studied through the thermodynamic approach of the associated solutions model that was introduced by Shakhmatkin and Vedishcheva in glasses. The weak electrolyte model and the Anderson and Stuart model have also been employed herein in order to calculate the activation energy of the conduction of lithium ions within the glass matrix. Experimental ionic conductivity and activation energy data have been determined and were compared with the ones calculated using the models mentioned above. The structural units of the network have also been obtained by means of the thermodynamic approach and compared with those determined by ^{31}P nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectra. All of them showed that the glass network structure can be reliably represented by a *solution* of chemical species and whose properties can then be derived from the respective weights in the system.

KEYWORDS

ionic conductivity, phosphates, thermodynamics

1 | INTRODUCTION

Lithium phosphates have since long been of importance to Materials Science research, not only for their interest with respect to the properties and structure of glass compositions¹⁻⁴

but also because of their implications for the development of novel and improved solid state electrolytes in battery research.^{5,6} The improvement of the ionic conductivity of solid electrolytes is of utmost importance in the design of safe, durable and energy and power dense electrochemical devices.⁵

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Although lithium phosphate glasses have limitations in the direct application as solid electrolytes, basically due to relatively poor chemical durability in humid atmospheres,⁶ they can be used as a base material for the production of improved electrolytes of technological interest,⁷ such as the so-called LiPON thin films for solid-state batteries.^{8–10} These LiPON films, which are generally obtained by physical deposition methods from Li_3PO_4 targets, have been found to be stable in contact with lithium metal in the range from 0 to 5 V,¹¹ establishing in this way its place in the market and allowing the use of lithium metal as the anode material.¹²

On the other hand, the research on lithium phosphate based glasses has become highly useful from the point of view of the mechanisms that control the ionic conduction throughout a glass network. The enhancement of the ion transport properties in lithium phosphate glasses can be done by different means, either through the increase of the content of charge carrier ions, which in parallel produces the depolymerization of the glass network as more Li_2O is added, or via the modification of the diffusion properties within the material, for example, by adding other elements such as nitrogen to the network.^{8–10} This correlation between depolymerization and ionic conductivity enhancement is due to the diffusion mechanism of Li^+ cations, consisting on thermally activated hopping between negatively charged positions, as the non-bridging oxygens (NBO).⁵ In a phosphate glass, the structural units that build up the network are $[\text{PO}_4]$ tetrahedral units that for a metaphosphate composition are arranged in the form of long chains or rings. Each group has then a net negative charge that is located on the NBO and with which the Li^+ ions are coordinated. As more lithium is added, the length of the chains decreases upon the formation of more NBO, thus enhancing the conductivity of the glass through the increase of the hopping positions for the lithium ions. On the other hand, it should be noted that in parallel to any structural modifications of the network, the increase of the number (concentration) of Li^+ ions does also contribute to the enhancement of ionic conductivity.

In the present study, the modeling of the ionic conductivity and activation energy for the conduction of these glasses has been made without using any adjustable parameters and by combining three existing models. The central part of this work has been done on the Shakhmatkin and Vedishcheva Thermodynamic Model (SVTDM) that has been previously applied very successfully in approaching the structure and thermodynamic properties of borate and borosilicate glasses.¹³ Furthermore, it has also been applied to the modeling of phosphate glasses; some of the systems being the $\text{CaO-P}_2\text{O}_5$ or $\text{BaO-P}_2\text{O}_5$.^{14,15} The model assumes that a glass is an ideal solution formed by the salt-like products formed from the reaction of the constituent oxides and the remaining unreacted oxides as well. In this model, the existence of complex groupings different from the salt-like products is neglected

and the association of the constituent oxides and the salt-like products is not taken into consideration.¹⁶ Furthermore, this model has the advantage of not using adjustable parameters. Assuming that the short-range structure of the glasses is similar to that of their corresponding crystalline species, Gibbs free energy functions of the salt-like groupings can be estimated from the ones of the corresponding crystalline compounds that constitute the equilibrium phase diagram of the system under study. These functions are necessary to carry out a calculation of the chemical equilibrium of the system. By doing so, it is then possible to elucidate the equilibrium molar amounts of all compounds for each composition, and thus, one can derive the distribution of the structural units present. From the chemical equilibrium, one can derive as well the total Gibbs free energy of the system, which allows us to calculate the volume properties that, as it will be presented below, will directly influence the content of mobile Li^+ species taking part of the conduction mechanism.

Furthermore, the Anderson and Stuart model (A&SM)¹⁷ has been used to calculate the activation energy for the conduction in the studied glasses.

2 | EXPERIMENT

2.1 | Preparation and characterization of glasses

Lithium phosphate glasses with composition $x \text{Li}_2\text{O}-(1-x) \text{P}_2\text{O}_5$ ($0.44 \leq x \leq 0.58$) have been prepared by conventional melt-quenching. Batches of 80 g were prepared by mixing Li_2CO_3 (Aldrich, 99%) and $\text{NH}_4\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4$ (Merck, 99%) in stoichiometric amounts. The batches were calcined in porcelain crucibles at 300°C and then melted for 2 h at temperatures ranging from 800°C to 950°C depending on the composition. Batches were poured onto a brass plate pre-heated at 300°C . A subsequent annealing treatment for 1 h at a temperature slightly above the glass transition temperature of the glasses was carried out.

Density (ρ) was measured at room temperature using Archimedes' principle and ethanol as the immersion liquid. Each measurement of sample weight was repeated four times.

Glass transition temperature, T_g , was determined by the dilatometry technique using a 402 EP dilatometer from Netzsch-Gerätebau, calibrated with an Al_2O_3 standard (ϕ 6×12 mm). Samples were cut in rectangular prisms whose base dimensions are $\sim 5 \times 5$ mm and length in the range of 11–15 mm. The heating rate was set to $5^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$.

Ionic conductivity was determined by the impedance spectroscopy technique, performed in a VMP3 impedance analyzer from BioLogic, in the frequency range from 10 to 10^6 Hz and temperatures between 50°C and 200°C . The samples were cut into disks of 1–2 mm in thickness and ~ 11 mm

in diameter and gold electrodes were sputtered on both faces as contacts for electrical measurements.

The Q^n structures were obtained from the ^{31}P magic angle spinning (MAS) nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectra, performed in a Bruker ASX 400 spectrometer at a frequency of 161.96 MHz, using a spinning frequency of 10 kHz in 4-mm rotors. The experiments were recorded with a 4- μs pulse length ($\pi/2$ pulse angle), a radio frequency (rf) strength of 60 kHz and 128 scans separated by a recycle delay (rd) of 60 s. Chemical shift values were referred to $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{HPO}_4$ at 0.82 ppm with respect to H_3PO_4 (85%). Prior to deconvolution, the spectra were simulated using Dmfit software.¹⁸

2.2 | Methods

The SVTDM assumes that a glass can be considered as a solution formed from products of the interaction between the oxide components. These products are called salt-like groupings. It is assumed that the stoichiometry of the groupings is similar to that of the crystalline compounds that exist in a given system (the structural similarity also exists, at least, in terms of the ratio). This guarantees the minimum Gibbs energy of a given system, and the glass of any composition can be represented by a superposition of various groupings. Thus, all the thermodynamic properties of the glasses can be derived from the Gibbs free energy expression of an ideal solution,¹⁶ that is, the equation of state of the system:

$$G = \sum n_i g_i + RT \sum n_j \ln(x_j) \quad (1)$$

where the molar Gibbs free energy (g_i) of each reaction product can be precisely estimated by using the expression of the function of the corresponding crystalline compound in the equilibrium phase diagram of the system, as the short-range structural order is very similar in both the glassy and the crystalline state.¹³ The i summation is taken only over the salt-like groupings, whereas that for j also includes the unreacted oxides.¹⁶

The equilibrium molar amount, n , of each salt-like product (j) and unreacted oxide (k) is obtained by solving a set of nonlinear equations composed by the mass balance and mass action laws of each reaction (j) that takes place in the system:

$$\begin{cases} K_j = \frac{x_j}{\prod_k x_k^{v_k^{(j)}}} & (2.1) \\ n_k^0 = n_k + \sum_j v_k^{(j)} n_j & (2.2) \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

These equations refer to the formation of chemical groupings from oxides, and the solution must satisfy the restriction $0 \leq n \leq 1$ for each equilibrium molar amount n . The

stoichiometric coefficients are denoted by the Greek letter ν and the equilibrium constants by the letter K . The superscript 0 denotes not the equilibrium molar amount but the initial one of each unreacted oxide.

In set of Equation (2), the equilibrium constants K_j of the mass action law (2.1) can be obtained from the free Gibbs free energies of the crystalline compounds: $K_j = \exp(-\Delta G_j/RT)$. The term n_k^0 of the mass balances (2.2) is the initial molar amount of each reacting oxide.

The solution of the nonlinear system 2 requires some kind of numerical approximation because, in general, it is not possible to calculate an analytical solution. The computation of the numerical approximation may be accomplished by using an iterative algorithm, but this procedure has two main drawbacks. On the one hand, the restriction that must satisfy n_i . On the other hand, the solution of x_j and n_k of system 2 can have some small-scale and large-scale values; this can lead to large numerical errors when computing the numerical solution. To avoid these numerical based errors associated to scale differences in the solution, it is convenient to reformulate the set of equations in problem 2. First, considering that

$$x_j = \frac{n_j}{\sum_i n_i} \quad (3)$$

and then taking the log in both sides of (2.1). In doing so, one can get the system

$$\begin{cases} \log K_j = \log n_j - \sum_k \nu_k \log n_j - \left(1 - \sum_k \nu_k\right) \log n \\ n_k^0 = n_k + \sum_j \nu_k^{(j)} n_j \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where $n = \sum_i n_i$. Finally, to avoid the numerical error associated to small and large values in the solution, we define $y_i = \log n_i$, then

$$\begin{cases} \log K_j = y_j - \sum_k \nu_k y_j - \left(1 - \sum_k \nu_k\right) \log n \\ n_k^0 = \exp(y_k) + \sum_j \nu_k^{(j)} \exp(y_j) \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

where, in this case, the restriction is $y_i \leq 0$.

The solution of this nonlinear system of equations can be approximated efficiently using many numerical algorithms. In this work, we employed the Matlab incorporated function *fsolve* that computes a numerical solution of a general nonlinear system of equations. In doing so, a Matlab code was developed to approximate numerically the solution for the full range of compositions (0.01 to 0.99 Li_2O content). Moreover, the code is also able to compute directly the Gibbs

free energy and specific heat of the system, again for all the full range of compositions.

A method for calculating the transport properties of oxide glasses from the SVTD model has been established by Shakhmatkin and Vedishcheva in previous works.^{13,14} In the case of ionic conductivity, the following expression is given for its calculation in¹³:

$$\log \sigma = \log \frac{2^{1/3} F \sum n_i}{V_m} + \log \mu_{\pm} + \frac{\Delta \mu_{M_2O} - \Delta G_D^0}{3 \cdot 2.303 RT} \quad (6)$$

where F is the Faraday constant, V_m is the glass molar volume, $\mu_{\pm} = \mu_+ + \mu_-$ is the total ionic mobility, ΔG_D^0 is the standard energy of dissociation, and $\Delta \mu_{M_2O}$ is the chemical potential of the modifier oxide.

Two of these quantities, ΔG_D^0 and μ_{\pm} , cannot be derived from thermodynamic magnitudes. However, the former is independent of the composition and nature of the system, and the latter is a weak function of the composition. Because of this, the sum of both terms is assumed to be a constant, and thus, σ could be calculated from Equation (6) within a constant deviation. However, this equation fails when predicting the ionic conductivity of lithium phosphate glasses, because of reasons that will be exposed in Section 3. Due to this fact, in the present work the weak electrolyte (WE) model¹⁹⁻²² and the Anderson and Stuart model (A&S)¹⁷ have been used along with the SVTD model as an alternative path to predict the ion transport properties in the $Li_2O-P_2O_5$ glasses. From the WE model, an Arrhenius expression is obtained for the product σT .²² This expression can be combined with the A&S model (to calculate the activation energy of the Arrhenius) and the SVTD model (to calculate the thermodynamic properties of the material) to predict the ionic conductivity of the glass.

In glasses, a Frenkel-type defect forming²² is assumed to be responsible of the conduction mechanism at low temperatures: the thermal vibrations are enough to make a network modifier (NWM) cation to jump from its equilibrium position (associated to an NBO) to an interstitial one when neighboring NBO positions are close enough. When this happens, the leaving cation, which is now in an interstitial position, will share another NBO with another cation, forming an interstitial-vacancy pair defect (Frenkel-type defect).¹⁹⁻²² In glasses, the concentration of this pair defects, n_+ , is very low in comparison with the total cation concentration, n (that is the reason because of which glasses are WEs), and the relationship between the last and the concentration can be described by the equation:

$$n_+ = n \exp \left(- \frac{\Delta G_f}{2 K_B T} \right) \quad (7)$$

where ΔG_f is the free energy that corresponds to the defect formation. By using the Einstein's equation for the conductivity, $\sigma = en_+ \mu_+$, it is thus possible to predict the conductivity

of the glasses, being e the charge of the electron and μ_+ the cation mobility.

The cation mobility, μ_+ , can then be calculated by considering the migration free energy (ΔG_m) in the glass structure²²:

$$\mu_+ = \frac{e \lambda^2 v_0}{6 K_B T} \exp \left(- \frac{\Delta G_m}{K_B T} \right) \quad (8)$$

where λ is the mean distance between cationic sites and v_0 is the jump attempt frequency, whose value is in the order of magnitude of $1.2 \cdot 10^{13}$ Hz for oxide glasses with Li_2O as modifier according to far-infrared spectroscopy results. This jump attempt frequency decreases with the decrease of the ionic field strength of the modifier cation, as it was demonstrated in $M_2O-P_2O_5$ glasses with $M = Li, Na$ and K .²³ Nonetheless, its value does not significantly changes when considering different ratios of the modifier to the former in the composition as it has also been seen in borate glasses,²⁴ and so it can be assumed that it will not experience a considerable change within the range of lithium contents studied. According to Exarhos and Rissen,²³ the value of v_0 for the $LiPO_3$ glasses was $1.2 \cdot 10^{13}$ Hz, which is the one to be used in Equation (5).

By using Equations (7) and (8) on Einstein's equation, the following expression for the product σT is obtained:

$$\sigma T = n \frac{e^2 \lambda^2 v_0}{6 k_B} \exp \left(- \frac{\frac{\Delta G_f}{2} + \Delta G_m}{k_B T} \right) \quad (9)$$

which is an Arrhenius-type equation of the form $A = A_0 \exp(-E_a/k_B T)$, where

$$\begin{cases} A_0 = n \frac{e^2 \lambda^2 v_0}{6 k_B} & (10.a) \\ E_a = \frac{\Delta G_f}{2} + \Delta G_m & (10.b) \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

The total Li^+ concentration can be calculated from number of moles of lithium and the molar volume predicted by the SVTD model: $n = 2 \cdot (n_{LP} + 2 \cdot n_{L2P} + 3 \cdot n_{L3P} + n_{Li_2O}) \cdot N_a / V_m$, where λ is calculated assuming isotropy through $\lambda = \sqrt[3]{1/n}$ and E_a is obtained from A&S model.

A&S model assumes that the required energy to move a cation is the sum of two contributions: a first which is necessary to move the cation (electrostatic energy change) to half of the jump distance presupposing that there is no change in the glass structure, and a second that is required to produce a deformation in the glass structure so as to produce a hole large enough for the cation to pass through (strain energy).

The electrostatic contribution (binding energy) can be approximated by using Coulomb's law for one ion pair (Coulombic energy)¹⁷:

$$E_e = Z_C Z_O q_e^2 \left(\frac{1}{R_C + R_{O^{2-}}} - \frac{2}{\lambda} \right) \quad (11)$$

where Z_C and Z_O are the valences of the cation and the oxygen, R_C and $R_{O^{2-}}$ are their ionic radii (60 pm for lithium and 140 for oxygen) and $q_e = 4.8 \cdot 10^{-10}$ esu is the fundamental charge. However, the use of this equation leads to too large activation energy values.

The explanation given by Anderson and Stuart¹⁷ for these results is that the electron cloud of O^{2-} anions is easily deformed by the NWM cation, lowering the binding energy, so Equation (7) must be modified to take into account this phenomenon. In order to do so, A&S introduced a “covalency parameter” (γ) in the equation:

$$E_e = \frac{Z_C Z_O q_e^2}{\gamma} \left(\frac{1}{R_C + R_{O^{2-}}} - \frac{2}{\lambda} \right) \quad (12)$$

A&S claimed that the value of this parameter is equal to the dielectric constant of the glass (empirical correlation). This assertion will be discussed in section below.

On the other hand, the second contribution (strain energy) to the activation energy can be calculated as the one which is needed to enlarge a doorway of radius r_D to the cation radius r , whose expression is¹⁷:

$$E_S = 4\pi G r_D (r - r_D)^2 \quad (13)$$

where G is the shear modulus of the glass. As $r_D = 0.6 a. u.$ for silica glasses^{17,25} and $r_{Li^+} \approx 0.6 a. u.$ as well, strain energy for phosphate glasses can be taken as null due to the fact that this kind of glasses is less compact than the silica ones (so r_D is expected to be even higher).

Regarding the glass molar volume, necessary to calculate the concentration n of the mobile cation, this can be calculated by using the SVTDM, which has been used in this work also in the prediction of the $Li_2O-P_2O_5$ glass structure (Q^n units).

3 | RESULTS

The results of solving problem of equations in (2) for the $Li_2O-P_2O_5$ system are shown in Figure 1A. The equilibrium molar amounts of each compound have been calculated at 1000 K to simulate the equilibrium liquid conditions, taking into account that the reaction of lithium oxide with phosphorus oxide can give rise to three different salt-like products: LP ($Li_2O \cdot P_2O_5$), L2P ($2Li_2O \cdot P_2O_5$), and L3P ($3Li_2O \cdot P_2O_5$) at 50%, 66.67%, and 75% of lithium oxide content, respectively, so set of Equation (2) becomes

FIGURE 1 Equilibrium composition diagrams for $Li_2O-P_2O_5$ glass system between 0 and 100 mol% Li_2O (A) and between $LiPO_3$ and Li_3PO_4 compositions (B)

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \log K_{LP} = \log \frac{n_{LP}}{\sum n} - \left(\log \frac{n_{Li_2O}}{\sum n} + \log \frac{n_{P_2O_5}}{\sum n} \right) \\ \log K_{L2P} = \log \frac{n_{L2P}}{\sum n} - \left(2 \log \frac{n_{Li_2O}}{\sum n} + \log \frac{n_{P_2O_5}}{\sum n} \right) \\ \log K_{L3P} = \log \frac{n_{L3P}}{\sum n} - \left(3 \log \frac{n_{Li_2O}}{\sum n} + \log \frac{n_{P_2O_5}}{\sum n} \right) \\ n_{Li_2O}^0 = n_{Li_2O} + n_{LP} + 2n_{L2P} + 3n_{L3P} \\ n_{P_2O_5}^0 = n_{P_2O_5} + n_{LP} + n_{L2P} + n_{L3P} \end{array} \right. \quad (14)$$

where $\sum n = n_{Li_2O} + n_{P_2O_5} + n_{LP} + n_{L2P} + n_{L3P}$ and n_i are the variables of the nonlinear equation system. The rest of the terms are known. Due to the requirements of the model formalism, we are working here with the groupings (LP, L2P, and L3P) rather than with the stoichiometry of the corresponding crystalline compounds ($LiPO_3$, $Li_4P_2O_7$, and Li_3PO_4), where the calculated equilibrium molar amounts correspond to the groupings.

The system has been solved for the whole range of composition, from $[n_{Li_2O}^0 = 0.01, n_{P_2O_5}^0 = 0.99]$ to $[n_{Li_2O}^0 = 0.99, n_{P_2O_5}^0 = 0.01]$, using a step of 0.01 and the variable change $y_i = \log n_i$.

FIGURE 2 ^{31}P MAS NMR spectra of the lithium phosphate glasses $\text{Li}_2\text{O}-\text{P}_2\text{O}_5$

Calculations are shown in Figure 1A. In Figure 1B, that shows results from the composition of LP to the L3P one, some disproportionation of L2P into LP and L3P groupings can be observed at 66.67% of Li_2O content. Values of the equilibrium constants of each salt-like product have been calculated by using the Gibbs free energies of the corresponding crystalline phases taken from FACT database, resulting in $\log_{10}(K^{\text{LP}}) = 20.8861514$, $\log_{10}(K^{\text{L2P}}) = 35.6023471$, and $\log_{10}(K^{\text{L3P}}) = 47.6684709$.

Figure 2 gathers the NMR spectra of the lithium phosphate glasses, all being formed by broad and symmetric peaks characteristic of resonances having chemical shift distribution in amorphous environments. The NMR spectra for glasses with <50 mol% Li_2O present signals peaks at -23 ppm and -38 ppm, corresponding to Q^2 and Q^3 PO_4 tetrahedra, respectively, while above 50 mol% Li_2O there remains a resonance at -20 ppm appearing a new one at ~ -5 ppm due to Q^1 terminal units. The Q^2 structures are given by the LP, which forms long chains and rings of PO_4 tetrahedra, each unit having two bridging oxygens (BO) and 2 NBO. Q^1 structures, with just 1 BO, are given by L2P. The weak Q^1 signal of the composition $x = 0.50$ is due to the end-of-chain PO_4 tetrahedra in LP chains as a result of a slight deviation from the stoichiometric composition. Figure 3 shows the result of the comparison of these experimental data with the calculated ones from solving set of Equation (14). In the ultraphosphate region, the fraction of Q^2 and Q^3 tetrahedra are given by $f(Q^2) = x/(1-x)$ and $f(Q^3) = (1-2x)/(1-x)$,²⁶ where x is the modifier oxide molar fraction. Between the metaphosphate ($x \leq 0.50$) and pyrophosphate ($x = 0.67$) boundaries, the fraction of Q^1 and Q^2 tetrahedra is given by the expressions $f(Q^1) = (2x-1)/(1-x)$ and $f(Q^2) = (2-3x)/(1-x)$.²⁶ Calculated values are in very good agreement with experiments, with a

FIGURE 3 Comparison between calculated values of Q^n groups at 1000 K, as represented by solid lines, and the experimental data from NMR simulations (symbols)

maximum difference of 2.32% between experimental and calculated values. Table 1 summarizes the results of the NMR simulations performed in these glasses together with the T_g values obtained from dilatometric measurements.

Figure 4 shows the comparison between the experimental molar volume of the glasses and the calculated using SVTDM using the following expression for this property:

$$V_m = \left(\frac{\partial G}{\partial p} \right)_{T, n_i} = \sum_j n_j v_j^{(c)} \quad (15)$$

where $v_j^{(c)}$ represents the molar volume of each crystalline compound and the unreacted oxides. Values of $v_j^{(c)}$ were calculated by using Korotkov's method,²⁷ which are listed in Table 2. As it is shown in Figure 4, values calculated from SVTDM agree reasonably well with molar volume data from measured density values, being the maximum error of 5% at the lithium metaphosphate (LP) composition. The experimental values of the glass densities and the molar volumes derived from them are listed in Table 3.

As it was mentioned in Section 2, the prediction of σ in $\text{Li}_2\text{O}-\text{P}_2\text{O}_5$ glasses fails when using Equation (6). In Figure 5, the calculated room temperature conductivity by Equation 3, and the associated chemical potential of Li_2O , has been represented against the Li_2O mol%. The conductivity values show a regular increase for compositions below and above 50 mol% Li_2O ; however, a big discontinuity is observed near the metaphosphate composition in the calculated conductivity, in the same manner than in the chemical potential values. The hypothesis that can be at the origin of this anomaly is that the dependence of μ_{\pm} on the composition is not so weak in this case, which is based in the following: as it can be

TABLE 1 ^{31}P isotropic chemical shift, full width half maximum (FWHM) and relative contents of Q^n phosphate species from MAS NMR spectra

% Li_2O (nominal)	T_g ($^\circ\text{C}$)	Q^n	^{31}P chemical shift (ppm)	FWHM (ppm)	Content (%)
44	n.d.	1	—	—	—
		2	-24.79	10.01	78.78
		3	-38.60	13.00	21.22
46	312	1	—	—	—
		2	-23.91	9.58	85.34
		3	-37.78	13.00	14.66
48	309	1	—	—	—
		2	-23.71	9.21	89.86
		3	-36.30	13.00	10.14
50	320	1	22126.20	8.63	2.32
		2	-23.19	9.22	97.68
		3	—	—	—
52	320	1	-4.58	6.92	10.26
		2	-22.55	9.31	89.74
		3	—	—	—
54	323	1	-4.42	6.56	17.87
		2	-22.32	9.56	82.13
		3	—	—	—
56	319	1	-4.26	6.26	26.74
		2	-21.89	9.70	73.26
		3	—	—	—
58	316	1	-4.07	6.29	38.12
		2	-21.17	10.14	61.88
		3	—	—	—

seen in Figure 1A, the top of each salt-like product amount line is sharp, except for the pyrophosphate as it can be observed in Figure 1B. However, in the preceding case studied by Shakhmatkin and Vedishcheva,^{14,16,28-30} or as shown in the results of the $\text{BaO-P}_2\text{O}_5$ system,¹⁵ the behavior is quite smooth. The studies cited above include not only phosphate glass systems but also borates, silicates or borosilicates. The reason for this might be the high ratio between the equilibrium constants of each salt-like product of the $\text{Li}_2\text{O-P}_2\text{O}_5$ system, which also causes a great change in the $\Delta\mu_{M_2O}$ value at the pure salt-like product composition (Figure 5). This causes the abrupt leap in the predicted values of σ if μ_{\pm} is considered independent of the composition.

Therefore, the ionic conductivity has been approached through the use of the calculated molar volumes obtained by the SVTDM in order to calculate n , the concentration of charge carrier, which is needed in Equation 9. Experimental and calculated values of ionic conductivity ($\text{Log } \sigma$) at 25°C and activation energy for the conduction are thus shown in

FIGURE 4 Experimental molar volume (symbols) and SVTDM calculated molar volume (solid lines) of $\text{Li}_2\text{O-P}_2\text{O}_5$ glasses. The lines are drawn as a guide for the eyes**TABLE 2** Calculated molar volume of the crystalline phases in $\text{Li}_2\text{O-P}_2\text{O}_5$ system from theoretical density data

Phase	Density (g cm^{-3})	V_m ($\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$)
P_2O_5	2.629	53.97
LiPO_3	2.444	35.15
$\text{Li}_4\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$	2.328	28.88
Li_3PO_4	2.249	25.74
Li_2O	1.830	16.33

TABLE 3 Experimental values of glass densities and the corresponding molar volumes

Li_2O (mol%)	Density (g cm^{-3})	V_m ($\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$)
58	2.3807	32.36
56	2.3751	33.38
54	2.3697	34.40
52	2.3387	35.81
50	2.3268	36.96
48	2.3186	38.06
46	2.3321	38.80

Figures 6 and 7, respectively, as a function of the molar content of Li_2O .

As it can be seen in Figure 6, the calculated values for $\text{Log } \sigma_{25^\circ\text{C}}$ follow the same increasing trend than the experimental values with the lithium content, in spite of the fact that there is a deviation in the value that makes the model to overestimate the calculated $\text{log } \sigma_{25^\circ\text{C}}$. This difference becomes larger for lower Li_2O contents although the calculated conductivity gets the same value as the experimental one above

FIGURE 5 Room temperature ionic conductivity and Li_2O chemical potential calculated from SVTDM for Li_2O - P_2O_5 system

FIGURE 6 Experimental and calculated $\log\sigma$ at 25°C as a function of composition. Lines represent least squares fits of data points. Ionic conductivity was calculated using Eq. 9, and activation energy calculated by the A&S model

55 mol% Li_2O and within the experimental error of the determination. Finally Figure 7 shows a very precise calculation of the activation energy for the product of σT for this system as the measured values fall very close the predicted ones from A&S model for the entire composition range of measurements.

4 | DISCUSSION

The present study combines three models so as to predict the ionic conductivity of lithium phosphate glasses. The first one is the A&SM that has been used to calculate the activation energy (E_a) of the ion transport mechanism at each composition. As it can be seen in Figure

FIGURE 7 Experimental and calculated activation energy of conduction as a function of composition. Lines represent least squares fits of data points

7, this model is able to predict not only the behavior of E_a as a function of the composition but also the actual value with a maximum error of 4.19% over the experimental values (inset of Figure 7), the rest of errors are below 3.5%. However, two remarks to this model have to be done concerning the way it has been calculated following A&S model. The first of them is that in the work of Anderson and Stuart,¹⁷ there is no explanation for the assignment of $\gamma = \epsilon$ (dielectric constant) beyond an empirical coincidence. In their work, Anderson and Stuart argued on the results for silicate glasses and considered a variety of hypothesis, but they also admitted that “it may only be fortuitous that the electrostatic forces, calculated on the assumption that silica glass can be represented by a collection of point charges, are reduced in the real glass

by a factor equal to the magnitude of the dielectric constant" as stated in Anderson and Stuart.¹⁷ An explanation for this correlation is thus needed in a future line of this work. Second, A&S studied only silica-based glasses for the calculation of E_a as mentioned above. In our work, however, a phosphate glass system has been studied and the results show that the calculation of E_a is also satisfactory taking the assumption of $\gamma = \epsilon \sim 10^1$ for phosphate glasses.⁴ What is more, no data of the dielectric constant as a function of composition are needed, only an approximate value to predict the E_a with a maximum error of 4.19% at $x_{\text{Li}_2\text{O}} = 0.48$, being the rest of errors below 3.5%. That means that an idea of the order of magnitude of this constant may be sufficient to obtain a precise result of activation energy, whose difference with the experimental one falls within the experimental error.

The model that we have used as basis for the calculation of the ionic conductivity in this work is the model of associated solutions that has been developed in glasses by Shakhmatkin and Vedishcheva. The results have shown that this model can be a good approximation to predict not only the structure of the glass system, with a maximum deviation of 2.32% in the prediction of Q^n structures, but also their volume properties, which are those needed in the last instance for the calculation of the ionic conductivity.

Regarding the molar volume, the maximum deviation with respect to the experimental value was found for the metaphosphate composition, with an error of 4.90%, as detailed in Section 3 and shown in Figure 4. Despite the experimental values present a linear decrease with the lithium content, the calculated volume shows a two slopes behavior, below and above the 50-mol% Li_2O . The cause for this maximum in the error at the metaphosphate composition may well be due to the approach followed in the calculation of the volume of LP grouping. On the other hand, it may be hypothesized that the degree of polymerization that gives rise to very long chains and rings produces an additional increase in the experimental molar volume measured, which contributes to a further separation with respect to the calculated volume of the crystalline LiPO_3 . These chains and rings would be more difficult to accommodate in the structure, increasing the free volume this way and, consequently, causing a higher deviation between the real value and the one calculated from Equation 15.

As seen in Figure 5, the calculated conductivity following the SVTDM approach is coherent with the chemical potential, as this is the dominant term in Equation (6). However, the very low absolute values of conductivity so obtained as compared with the experimental ones indicate that the calculation of conductivity following this approach could not be done without the ionic mobility and dissociation energy and their variation with composition.

The deviation from experimental values observed in Figure 6 cannot be due to an error in the calculation of E_a (see Figure 6); therefore, a higher impact on the calculated conductivity is expected from the pre-exponential term (Equation 10), where F and k_B are constants and v_0 shows little variation with the composition,²³ while n and λ depend on the calculated V_m . The results of conductivity gathered in Figure 6 have been obtained from the molar volume values as calculated from the SVTDM model, so a parallel calculation of $\text{Log}_{10}\sigma_{25^\circ\text{C}}$ has been performed using in this case the experimental values of V_m , so as to check if this is the source of discrepancy. The E_a has also been calculated in this way, as it also depends on V_m , but the maximum deviation between the two values of E_a (one using calculated V_m values and the other using experimental ones) is 0.34% only, so no significant influence on the conductivity is assumed after this checking. The calculated conductivity using experimental V_m provides the same values than using the calculated V_m and so, again, this possibility can be discarded.

A final consideration may be done regarding the differences observed in the slope of increase of conductivity, which is higher for the measured values and approach the calculated conductivity at the highest Li_2O contents studied within the limits of experimental error. As it was described in Section 2.2, the calculation of the ionic conductivity has been done assuming that the conduction takes place inside an isotropic medium, for which the average distance between hopping positions, λ , is taken as $\lambda = \sqrt[3]{1/n}$ and n the number of charge carriers per volume. However, despite the fact that the calculated conductivity remains higher than the experimental one within the range of compositions studied, the higher rate of increase of the experimental conductivity could be argued to be caused through the arrangement of lithium coordination polyhedra, LiO_n ($n = 4-5$), in a sort of percolation channels where the last would be linked through O-Li-O bonds. This was concluded in the work by Alam et al. on ^6Li and ^7Li NMR investigations of the binary lithium phosphate glasses,³¹ and as it was stated therein, the connection of lithium polyhedra would induce a repolymerization starting above 25 mol% Li_2O that is thought to also be responsible of the increase in the glass transition temperature for all compositions above that lithium content. In this sense, the experimental conductivity would be approaching the theoretical one calculated for an isotropic distribution of lithium cations, and even surpassing it above some Li_2O content near 60 mol%.

It would however remain unexplained the smaller absolute values of experimental conductivity within the studied range and that could not be attributed to any particular effect of molar volume or covalency parameter as discussed above. In another work by Alam et al.,³² where the authors extended their structural study through 2-D NMR experiments in lithium phosphate glasses, it is reviewed the possibilities of network organization based on the

experimental data on the connectivity of the Q^n structural groups. Therein, it was pointed out that the introduction of Li_2O to a P_2O_5 network would induce a depolymerization throughout the formation of separated microdomains rich in either Q^3 or Q^2 groups. Then, for intermediate lithium contents, and similar to the range that we have studied in the present work, the network would be composed of “microdomains where a connective tissue allows for the ionic migration”,³² similarly to the modified random network (MRN) model that was introduced before by Greaves.³³ If the phosphate glass network is then composed of microdomains, some more polymerized and so with smaller contents of lithium than others, the measured conductivity may thus be smaller because the conduction paths will only occur within the regions where the lithium ions are concentrated. Therefore, as opposed to an ideal isotropic distribution of modifiers throughout the network, there would be non-connected regions through which the conduction is interrupted, and most importantly at lower Li_2O contents, and resulting in a bigger difference between calculated and measured conductivity with the decrease of the modifier content. This difference between calculated and experimental conductivity is progressively reduced as the Li_2O content increases via linking of LiO_n polyhedra that enhance the conduction creating more effective pathways.

Despite the limitations in the calculation of some of the properties that have been reviewed above, the thermodynamic model of Shakhmatkin and Vedishcheva has demonstrated to be useful in the modeling of the structure and physicochemical properties of oxide glasses and most particularly of compositions that show a high interest for their application as solid-state electrolytes. As a future line of research, our group is already working on the development of this modeling on mixed anion chemistries, such as the oxynitride phosphates, among which the LiPON electrolytes are a very well-known example and whose conduction properties have already been interpreted from experimental measurements.³⁴ On the other hand, the method will also need to be adjusted for calculations on ternary and higher order systems where the presence of a couple of network formers or different modifiers will influence not only the structural units but also the transport properties of the glasses and notably their ionic conduction.

5 | CONCLUSIONS

Despite the nonequilibrium conditions of the glassy state, its structure can be well represented through the approximation of the g_i of each salt-like grouping by its homologous crystalline phase, demonstrating a very high accuracy in the present case. On the other hand, in combination with the WE

and Stuart and Anderson approaches, the thermodynamic modeling permits to calculate the room temperature conductivity and activation energy of the conduction mechanism, both showing very close values to the experimentally determined ones. Finally, this study evidenced once more that the Shakhmatkin and Vedishcheva model allows the chemical structure and volume properties of lithium phosphate glasses to be accurately predicted.

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